



Have you tested for HIV in the last 2 months? Yes / No

If YES, was it a self-test? Yes / No

If YES, did you take that test at a football event? Yes / No

How old are you?

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If YES, did you take that test at a football event? Yes / No

Are you Male or Female? Male / Female